

FAILURE TESTING OF LARGE COMPOSITE AEROSPACE STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY

Large composite aerospace structures were tested to failure under flight-like static load conditions. Through rigorous test discipline and testing of relevant aerospace hardware, this research program provides previously unavailable experimental data to validate and augment current and advanced analytical techniques.

Keywords: testing, failure, static loads, composites, aerospace structures

OVERVIEW

CSA Engineering, under technical direction from the Air Force Research Laboratory Space Vehicles Directorate (AFRL/RV), has performed structural failure testing on key, large aerospace composite structures. The static load failure testing continues load application above previously applied flight and qualification load levels until structural failure was achieved. The test program was rigorously controlled to most effectively impart flight-like loading scenarios, thereby demonstrating the limiting structural failure mechanism and gross load capacity during actual flight conditions.

Instrumentation and video cameras were used to record significant events to determine failure initialization and propagation and to correlate with analytical predictions for structural response and ultimate failure. Such predictions are typically driven by data attained through composite coupon tests, uninspired analytical techniques, and company specific knock-down factors encompassing a host of potential issues, real or assumed. It is, therefore, not surprising to learn that the composite structure designs error on the side of being overly conservative.

EXPERIMENTAL OBJECTIVES

Three test articles, shown in Figure 1, were chosen as viable candidates for the failure testing program. Each test article represents a unique composite structure designed to be flown on a specific launch platform. While they are unique, the test articles are rather standard aerospace composite structures that typify the design to manufacturing to flight cycle common with all launch vehicle companies. Missing from this cycle is one critical data point, quantifiable structural failure. From the onset of this experimental program, the objective was clearly defined to find that missing piece and give back to the design community valuable information that, without it, prevents design optimization for large, aerospace, composite structures.

As a precursor to failure testing, the articles were subjected to a static load qualification test defined as 125% of the specified launch environment (i.e. 125% of the predicted flight loads). It is commonly accepted that a structure is flight-worthy after successfully demonstrating structural integrity at qualification load levels, with little-to-no consideration given to the actual margin of safety, the primary failure mechanism, and how the structure can be improved. The following discussion is intended to detail the specifics of the testing program and to summarize the overall results. A more in-depth analysis of the finite element modelling techniques used for the structural designs and failure predictions as well as scrutinized test data will be presented in subsequent publications.

Figure 1: Failure Test Articles: (L) Composite Adapter for Shared Payloads (CASPAR), (C) InterStage Adapter (ISA), (R) 1780 Payload Attach Fitting (PAF)

TEST CONFIGURATION

All loads were applied to the test articles with hydraulic actuators controlled via an MTS Aero-90 LT load control system. Load application was intended to be static, but was technically quasi-static with a slow, but constant ramp rate. While each test article presents its own load application challenges, loads are typically applied directly to a load head attached either directly to the test article or separated from the test article with an adapter. Such an adapter may be a necessity to accurately emulate a flight-like boundary condition at critical interfaces, complete with representative axial, radial, and bending stiffnesses, in-tolerance mechanical interfaces, and the specified load peaking distribution across the mating interfaces. As described in the following sections, each test setup is tailored to the unique test article configuration and to the unavoidable limitations inherent in ground-based testing.

A host of instrumentation was implemented to monitor and capture significant events leading up to and including test article failure. Physical measurements were captured in the form of load cell, strain gage, and displacement transducer readings. Applied loads were monitored and controlled with load cells mounted to each actuator shaft, providing the feedback signal to the load control system. Pre-test analytical efforts were used to identify critically strained and likely failure regions to be monitored with strain gages during the tests. Additional strain gages were applied in more innocuous locations to monitor the overall structural response and to give an indication of gross stiffness transitions due to localized structural failure. Used in a similar capacity, displacement sensors were used to measure and monitor the overall structural stiffness and stiffness changes. To augment the physical data, each test was recorded with digital video cameras focused on the predicted failure regions.

CASPAR

The test program started with the qualification and failure testing of CASPAR. This structure was designed to carry multiple payloads aboard the Minotaur IV launch vehicle through optimizing the available payload envelop. CASPAR consists of two symmetric, 74-inch diameter solid composite laminate shells connected at the mid-plane with a separation system. Each shell consists of a cylindrical section starting at the separation plane that transitions to an inward conical taper and finally to a flat, all-composite flange for connecting to the launch vehicle and payload. A single access door is located in the cylindrical section and there are four vent holes evenly spaced in the tapered regions of each shell. Functionally, CASPAR will house either a single payload or multiple smaller payloads within the composite cylinders while providing a standard payload interface at the forward flange for an additional payload or payloads as shown in Figure 2. The satellites will be deployed by separating the external payload(s) followed by the CASPAR shell separation and, finally, internal payload(s) separation.

Figure 2: Notional CASPAR Launch Configuration [1]

The initial, CASPAR qualification testing was completed in January 2008. The test series was comprised of eight individual loading scenarios subjecting the structure to various combinations of axial compressive or tensile load coupled with an applied lateral and moment loads. A smooth-wall stiffness adapter was bolted to both the forward and aft CASPAR flanges, providing a flight-like estimate of those boundary conditions, and all loads were applied to a welded and machined steel load head. No loads were applied to represent the internal payload stack because there is no direct load transfer between the internal payload(s) and the CASPAR structure. As designed, CASPAR and the internal payload stack simply share a flange with the launch vehicle's adapter with no load interactions with the composite shell.

The basic qualification test stack is shown in Figure 3 below. Thirty-three uni-axial strain gages and 22 strain gage rosettes, a total of 99 strain channels, were installed on the test article based on pre-test analytical models. In addition, six displacement transducers were mounted to measure the axial displacements of the forward and aft flanges. All strain and displacement channels were monitored and recorded during each of the eight qualification tests.

Figure 3: CASPAR Qualification Test Stack

During failure test design, a number of modifications were made to ensure a useful, composite failure was achieved before an undesirable failure—in this case, a failure in the stiffness adapter. Pre-test analyses demonstrated significant yielding and potential failure of the aft stiffness simulator before reaching critical strain limits within CASPAR, so it was removed. A thick, 5.1 cm (2.0 in) aluminium plate was subsequently used to provide the correct bolt circle pattern to the reaction frame and test article. While the stiffness simulator removal certainly changed the aft boundary condition, the analysis showed little affect on the overall strain distribution. The test stack is shown in Figure 4 along with the actuators and the structure used to react the actuator loads (reaction structure).

Figure 4: CASPAR Failure Test Setup

The most significant change made prior to failure testing was in the ratio of applied axial, shear, and moment loads. By transforming the applied qualification loads to equivalent line loads at the aft flange, it quickly became apparent that CASPAR failure can be driven and directed by simply increasing the compressive line load. To do so, the two 100 Kip actuators were used to apply purely axial load in the amount of 180 kN (40,500 lbs) while simultaneously applying a lateral load of 159 kN (35,760 lbs) at an elevation of 2.6 m (102.4 in) above the aft flange. Because of the moment created by the lateral load, the aft flange, maximum, compressive line load is found at and directed to one discrete azimuth. To meet the objectives of the test, this azimuth was chosen to be 180° opposite the aforementioned access doors. When normalized to equivalent, compressive line loads, the chosen failure load case can be said to represent 884% of the

predicted flight environment as defined prior to qualification testing. It is important to emphasize that this 884% level is not a prediction of failure; rather it is the maximum level of load that can be applied.

CASPAR failure detailed results and comparison of experimental to analytical data are the subject of another publication [2]. Suffice it to say that the structure was successfully tested to failure and excellent data were collected. There were four notable events prior to catastrophic failure as summarized in Table 1. Listed are the predictions and recorded load levels at which the specific event happened. The first two, ‘Separation System Gapping’ and ‘Access Door Doubler Bond Failure,’ were certainly not catastrophic failures, but played a roll in the progression from a pristine test article to a failed test article. Aft joint compression failure, shown to initiate at 792%, is believed to have begun sooner, but was not apparent until then. Even though the aft joint shows failure spanning the entire distance between the two vent holes on the compressive side, this was not considered a catastrophic failure because the test article continued to maintain load carrying capacity. Final, catastrophic failure occurred at 847%, and is believed to be from ‘Open Hole Tension’ failure at the two vent holes. At this point, the structure lost significant stiffness and load carrying capacity. Post-test pictures of the failed test article are shown in Figure 5.

Table 1: CASPAR Failure Test Events

Demonstrated Level (% Limit Load)	Predicted Level (% Limit Load)	Event Description
232-268	253	Separation System Gapping
534	283	Access Door Doubler Bond Failure
792	600	Aft Joint Composite Compression
847	620	Open Hole Tension Failure at Aft Vent Hole

Figure 5: CASPAR Failure Locations: (L) Aft Joint Compression Failure, (R) Open Hole Tension Failure

InterStage Adapter

The second test article chosen, the CCB Conical ISA, is shown in relation to the rest of the Atlas V 400 series launch vehicle in Figure 6. The conical ISA is comprised of a graphite-epoxy composite structure with aluminium mating flanges at the forward and aft interfaces. Functionally, the ISA is used to adapt the CCB 3.81 m (12.5 ft) diameter to the Centaur 3.0 m (10 ft) diameter, having an overall height of 1.6 m (5.4 ft) and mass of 418 kg (922 lbs).^{3, 4}

The ISA test article was manufactured as a qualification test unit prior to flight production. Being the baseline unit for subsequent flight units, the qualification structure is identical to the proposed flight units. The ISA is a simple conic having only one significant feature, the access door shown in Figure 7 below. Added layers of composites, or pad-ups, surround the perimeter of the door to compensate for the loss in stiffness at the cut-out.

During the qualification test program, a low-level version of the proposed failure test was run to gain further insight into the structure's response once proposed failure test setup changes were implemented. For qualification testing, two flight-like stiffness adapters were installed at the forward and aft ISA interfaces. These adapters were designed to accurately represent the boundary conditions of the Common Core Booster and the Centaur ISA-Short—the qualification test stack is shown in Figure 8. Similar to the CASPAR test, it was determined that the loads required to fail the composite ISA would likely result in failure of either stiffness adapter first. To avoid this unintended failure, both stiffness adapters were removed for failure testing, resulting of a simplified test stack of the ISA bolted directly to the base plate (10.2 cm (4.0 in) thick steel plate) and bolted directly to the load head.

Figure 6: Atlas V 400 Series Launch System⁵

Figure 7: The ISA Qualification Structure

Figure 8: ISA Qualification Test Stack

Data from the low-level, pre-failure test were used to quantify the consequences of removing these stiffness adapters. Analyses showed the high-strain and likely failure region to be the upper corner of the access door while subjected to excessive compressive loads. By removing the upper stiffness simulator, the Centaur ISA-Short adapter, and bolting directly to the stiffer load head, a modest, but significant change in this strain state would be apparent as the load head provides a more fixed boundary condition. To compare these two loading configurations, the qualification test stack was loaded to an amount equivalent to 38% of the maximum flight compressive load. After the initial failure run, the principal strains at the upper door corner were compared as shown in Figure 9. By linearly projecting the pre-failure data from 38% to 200%, it is estimated that the maximum principal strains of the failure test setup are reduced by 15.1% and 43.7% on the outside and inside surfaces respectively and the minimum principal strains are reduced by 13.4% and 20.3%. These factors are used to correct the failure loads in the proceeding discussion, but will be considered estimates only since they cannot be verified.

Figure 9: Principal Door Strains – Pre-Failure and Failure Runs

Due to test hardware limitations, the maximum compressive load that could be applied was constrained to 200% of the worst-case compressive flight load at the ISA forward flange. This is equivalent to a compressive load of 5,712 kN (1,284,000 lbs) and is oriented directly down the left door edge when facing the test article from the outside. Because the door has significant composite pad-ups around the door, the failure test did

not show any sign of failure, a situation that was predicted prior to testing. To ensure failure, a second door identical in geometry and manufacturing technique was cut in the ISA 180° opposite the original. The idea being a useful composite failure could be developed at the same location with a door containing no reinforced pad-ups. The original loads, consisting of axial, shear, and moment loading had to be reversed to clock the maximum compression load 180°.

Strain gages totalling 125 channels were used for failure testing, most of which were a subset of the initial qualification test series. Additional gages were added to mirror those used around the original door to the new door, including two, back-to-back rosettes at the predicted failure region, the upper door corner. Thirteen displacement sensors were located on the outside ISA surface near the forward flange, the mid-plane, and the aft flange. Video cameras were situated to capture both a more full-field view and a localized view of the upper door corner.

The second, new door failure attempt was a success, with the structure exhibiting catastrophic failure at approximately 183%. Principal strain data collected during the final failure run are shown alongside the corrected and predicted data in Figure 10. Again, the corrected data are merely scaling of the raw data and are reported simply to graphically show an estimate of differences in the load state with and without the adapters. Catastrophic structural failure initiated from the predicted upper door corner, and propagated around the circumference as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 10: Principal Door Strains – Raw Data and Estimated Corrected Data

Figure 11: ISA Failure

1780 PAF

Rounding out the test articles was the Delta IV 1780 Payload Attach Fitting (PAF). Aboard the Delta IV, this PAF is one of a suite of structures offered to provide a standard interface for payload attachment. This is a purely conical and symmetrical structure void of any additional design features. This specific test article is a developmental unit intended to demonstrate the validity of an all-composite flange designed to replace the standard, metallic forward flange. The structure has a tapered core that terminates to solid composite near the forward flange. At the time of this publication, the PAF failure test has been completed, but did not meet all of its primary objectives. As with the other two tests, a stiffness adapter, a thick aluminium conical shell used for the qualification testing, had to be removed from the PAF forward flange for failure load application. With this adapter removed, the PAF flange was attached directly to the load head comprised of a 12.7 cm (5 in) thick steel plate. Pre-test analyses left the team undecided on whether or not the test article could be failed in a meaningful manner with such a drastic change in the forward boundary condition.

Currently, the results of the failure test are being evaluated and are not completed with sufficient detail to be presented in this paper. Post-test observations indicate that a useful composite structural failure was not achieved; rather, the forward flange was merely damaged when a series of fasteners failed during testing. The damage shown in Figure 12 shows the composite failure noted at the forward flange in the failed fastener region. The current course of action is to review the collected data and video, and to revisit the pre-test finite element models to replicate the fastener failure.

Figure 12: PAF Forward Flange Composite Failure

CONCLUSIONS

Failure test design for each article is tailored to achieve the combined loading state witnessed during operation and to capture sufficient experimental data for post failure analyses. Each test was designed to initiate a failure mode representing a flight-like scenario that produces a catastrophic composite failure—a challenge that requires balancing the issues inherent in ground based testing with driving a composite failure that is relevant to the designer and the community. Results presented in this study indicate considerable mass savings could be achieved if improved analytical methods were available during the design stages of these large composite articles. The authors attribute the inability of the aerospace community to accurately predict the behavior of composite structures to material uncertainties, manufacturing uncertainties, and analytical uncertainties that ultimately preclude the optimal use of composite materials

in space-born applications. Further data reduction and post-test analyses will continue with the hope that the final results will provide some valuable and currently unavailable failure data to the designers of future composite aerospace structures.

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